

1 **PRDM1 activates Ddx17, an Xist-interacting helicase.**

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6 We describe PRDM1 regulation of an Xist interacting helicase, DDX17, which itself was sufficient to
7 control aspects of the oncogenic program. The data support a role for PRDM family molecules in
8 transformation, provide additional evidence for a dominant contribution of the Xist imprinting system in
9 transformation, and provide enhanced detail describing nuclear processes which serve as the molecular
10 basis for transformation in humans (cancer). Helicase control of transformation-associated homeoboxes
11 has not yet been described.

12 Citations

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Results

Figure 1: PRDM1 activates the Ddx17 helicase.

GSE157206
GSE233342

Figure 2: Ddx17 is an Xist interacting protein

Figure 3: Rad51 depletion activates Ddx17.

GSE54266

Figure 4: Ddx17 depletion activates PRDM1.

GSE173292

Figure 5: Ddx17 depletion associated with PRDM1 mobilization results in induction of DUXAP homeobox transcription factors, nuclear factors that occupy specific positions in the hierarchy of homeobox factors that execute transformation resulting in ECT2 induction.

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Figure 6. Ddx17 depletion mobilizes imprinting machinery, influences genomic stability, and activates and represses molecules with transformation potential.

- a. SLX1A and SLX1B expression was lost.
- b. Dzip3 expression was lost.
- c. Ssbp3 expression was lost.

- d. Smarcd1 and SS18 were activated.
- e. SLBP expression was lost.
- f. RIG-I was activated.

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